

A Simulation Study of Multiple Imputation Methods Applied to Missing Covariates in Meta-Regression

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Abstract

Meta-analysis is a statistical method for quantitatively synthesizing primary study evidence. Meta-regression is used to assess whether study-level predictors can explain a part of heterogeneity in the results of primary studies. The problem of missing data can arise when primary studies do not provide candidate predictors for meta-regression, but there is insufficient research on how to deal with that. It is implied that the majority of meta-regressions using a single covariate might be due to the fact that increasing the number of covariates makes it more difficult to deal with the problem of missing data. Multiple imputation is well established and practical method for missing data, while it is known that its use in the context of missing covariates and the use of weights in the imputation model should be carefully considered. In this presentation, we will discuss how to deal with missing covariates in meta-regression using multiple imputation methods. Especially, the algorithms and models of the imputation methods, including weighted regression, will be compared under the settings of various missing mechanisms via simulation studies.

Key Words: meta-analysis, meta-regression, missing data, multiple imputation

1. Background

Meta-analysis is a statistical method used when quantitative evidence can be synthesized in a series of systematic reviews. Because of the substantial or methodological diversity of each primary study included in the meta-analysis, the true effect in each study is not the same, i.e., there might be heterogeneity. When considering the heterogeneity, a random-effects model is used instead of a fixed-effects model to handle the heterogeneity, but it is important to examine the factors that cause heterogeneity (Thompson, 1994). A meta-regression model tries to predict the study's effect size and account for the heterogeneity, based on characteristics of studies. In the context of meta-regression, the problem of missing data can arise when candidate covariates for meta-regression are not presented in each primary study. However, there is insufficient research on how to deal with the problem of missing covariates in meta-regression. Pigott and Polanin (2020) recommended applying multiple imputation (MI) (Rubin, 1987) when covariates are missing and comparing the results with those of CC and noted that further research on how to deal with missing covariates is needed.

MI is well established as a practical method when missingness occurs under the missing at random (MAR) assumption. White and Carlin (2010) pointed that while MI is more efficient than CC across a wide range of scenarios, however, MI is not always better than CC so that it is important to consider the missing mechanism in detail on individual studies. Recently, a simulation study for meta-regression with missing covariates have shown that using MI or full information maximum likelihood (FIML) may be preferable to ad hoc methods including CC (Lee & Beretvas, 2023). However, the authors conducted their evaluation only under MAR conditions and did not use the

weight for each primary study in their imputation model and noted that the imputation model may be mis-specified and fails to recognize precision-weighting in meta-regression.

In this presentation, we extend the work of Lee and Beretvas (2023) and evaluate MI methods to deal with missing covariates in the context of meta-regression. Specifically, the algorithms and models of the imputation methods, including weighted regression, will be compared under the settings of various missing mechanisms via simulation studies.

2. Methods

2.1 Meta-regression model

The meta-regression model in this study considers the case where a single independent estimated effect size and study-level covariates are available from each primary study. Let $\hat{\delta}_j$ be the effect size estimated from study j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, J$), and let $\mathbf{X}_j = (1, x_{j1}, \dots, x_{jp})$ be a vector consisting of p covariates and an intercept. The random-effects meta-regression model is

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{\delta}_j &= \mathbf{X}_j \boldsymbol{\beta} + u_j + e_j \\ u_j &\sim N(0, \tau^2) \\ e_j &\sim N(0, s_j)\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_p)'$ is a vector of fixed-effects unknown parameters. A random-effect u_j represents between-study heterogeneity, which cannot be explained using covariates and follows a normal distribution with mean of zero and heterogeneity variance τ^2 . The error term e_j represents sampling error of effect size in each primary study and is independent of u_j . For each study's estimated effect size, the standardized between-group mean difference (SMD), which is the difference in means between two independent groups, standardized by the pooled standard deviation is used. We used Hedges'g, which is modified SMD, taking into account small-sample bias, consistent with Lee and Beretvas (2023).

2.2 Imputing methods

In our research, we focus on Multivariate Imputation by Chained Equations (MICE) algorithm (van Buuren, Boshuizen, & Knook, 1999) and use a method called Bayesian linear regression based on White, Royston, and Wood (2011). A linear regression model is the most common choice of model for imputing normally distributed continuous variables. In this study, however, it is not appropriate to assume homoscedasticity due to weights of each primary study, so that we use weighted regression model and parameters are estimated by a generalized least squares, instead of ordinary least square method.

Lee and Beretvas (2023) used the predicted mean matching (PMM) without considering weights, which is the default imputation algorithm in R package mice. PMM is a method to impute actually observed values close to the predicted value from the posterior predictive distribution. We will compare 'PMM' to Bayesian regression 'MI', in which the predicted value from the posterior predictive distribution is used as is. Furthermore, we will examine the methods where the regression model used in the algorithm for each imputation model is a weighted regression model (shown as 'wPMM' and 'wMI'), and also where weights are included in impute model as an explanatory variable (shown as 'ExW').

2.3 Simulation studies

In the simulation studies, relative parameter bias (RPB) and coverage were evaluated using MI (PMM, MI, wPMM, wMI, ExW) compared to CC for missing covariates in meta-regression. The analysis was also performed using the complete data before the generation of the missing values as positive control. The results are denoted as 'Full' to distinguish them from the CC results. Furthermore, as a reference when examining the impact of considering weights, a setting was established in which Full data is used but weights are not considered in the analytical model, and this setting is denoted as 'No-w'. As in Lee and Beretvas (2023), an absolute value of 0.05 or less is assumed as a practically acceptable threshold for RPB. In each iteration of the simulation,

complete data were first generated, and then missing values were generated based on not only MAR, but also missing completely at random (MCAR) and missing not at random (MNAR).

All of meta-regression models were conducted using the R-package metafor (Viechtbauer, 2005) and all imputations were performed using the R package mice (van Buuren & Groothuis-Oudshoorn, 2011) and miceadds (Robitzsch, Grund, & Henke, 2024).

2.3.1 Data generation

We simulated data based on meta-regression model (1) where the number of covariates p was set to three. The fixed-effects parameters $\boldsymbol{\beta} = (\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_3)'$ were set to $(0.1, 0.2, 0.05, 0)'$ and $\mathbf{X}_j = (1, x_{j1}, \dots, x_{j3})$. For simplicity, the covariates were assumed to be standardized continuous quantities and generated according to a multivariate normal distribution with correlation coefficients ρ . According to (1), we calculated true study specific SMD $\hat{\delta} = \mathbf{X}_j\boldsymbol{\beta} + u_j$ where $u_j \sim N(0, \tau^2)$ for study j , then the error term e_j in (1) was captured through generating individual outcome in the same as Lee and Beretvas (2023), as follows:

$$y_{tij} \sim N(\delta_j, 1), \quad y_{c_{ij}} \sim N(0, 1)$$

Here, the individual outcome data are y_{tij} for participant i in the treatment (t) group of study j and the same as $y_{c_{ij}}$ in the control (c) group.

Table 1 Scenario settings in the simulation studies

Scenario	Number of primary studies	Sample size in primary studies	% of Missingness	Heterogeneity
1	100	Small: U (20, 50)	5	0
2	100	Small: U (20, 50)	10	0
3	100	Small: U (20, 50)	20	0
4	100	Small: U (20, 50)	20	0.2
5	20	One-small: one study with 20 cases and otherwise, U (100, 200)	5	0
6	20	One-small: one study with 20 cases and otherwise, U (100, 200)	10	0
7	20	One-small: one study with 20 cases and otherwise, U (100, 200)	20	0

In the simulation study, we used scenarios in which number of primary studies, sample size in primary studies, missingness rates, and between-study heterogeneity were varied (Table 1). Scenarios 1 – 4 are conditions with relatively large number of primary studies for a meta-analysis and are used to compare PMM and ordinary MI. In the remaining scenarios 5 – 7, we confirmed whether MI is still effective in conditions where the number of primary studies is small and search for conditions where weighted imputation is particularly effective. For simplicity, the heterogeneity variance τ^2 was set to 0 in most scenarios expect 4 in Table 1. The number of participants in each group is assumed to follows uniform distribution.

2.3.2 Missing data mechanisms

In this study, a logistic regression model was used to generate the missing data. The missing probability π_{j1} for a covariate x_{j1} is generated as follows:

$$\log\left(\frac{\pi_{j1}}{1 - \pi_{j1}}\right) = \phi_0 + \phi_1 x_j^* + \phi_2 x_{j2}^* + \phi_3 x_{j3}^* + \phi_4 \delta_j^*$$

Here, the asterisk indicates a standardized value, e.g. δ_j^* is the standardizes Hedges'g in study j . In order to examine the MCAR and MNAR mechanisms as well as the MAR, four scenarios for the missing mechanism were prepared and are shown in Table 2. The same mechanism applied to x_{j2}

and x_{j3} , but MNAR will be considered only for x_{j1} . ϕ_0 was adjusted as the probabilities of missing are 5, 10 or 20 %. The number of iterations in each scenario is 2000.

Table 2 Parameter settings about missingness mechanism

Scenario	MCAR	MAR	MNAR
ϕ_0	$\neq 0$	$\neq 0$	$\neq 0$
ϕ_1	0	0	2
ϕ_2	0	2	2
ϕ_3	0	2	2
ϕ_4	0	2	2

3. Results

3.1 Method comparison

Results for simulated data sets in scenario 1 – 4, which have 100 small studies per one NMA are in Figure 1. Hereafter, β_0 , which represents the effect size, will be referred to as the intercept, and β_1 will be referred to as the slope. Results for β_2 and β_3 are not shown, regarding those as auxiliary variables, but are included in both the imputation and analysis models. Figure 1 shows that there is no substantial bias when missingness mechanism is MCAR across all conditions. Except for the conditions using complete data, bias occurred in intercept under MAR and MNAR conditions and increased as the proportion of missingness was large, while little bias was found with respect to slope except for the CC. The point that the use of PMM has a greater impact than the use of weights in this condition in these scenarios.

Figure 1: The Relative parameter bias (RPB) for the intercept and the slope estimates with the meta-regression model by method handling missing data, missing mechanisms, and the scenarios (1 – 4). The x-axis refers to the method used for handling the missing data: CC, complete-case analysis; PMM, predictor mean matching; wPMM, weighted predictor mean matching; MI, normal Bayesian imputation; wMI, weighted normal Bayesian imputation; ExW, weight used as an explanatory variable; Full, Analysis using complete data; and No-w, Weights are not considered in the analysis model using complete data.

3.2 Special cases for the sample sizes of primary studies

To search the advantage of considering weights in the MI prediction model, results for special scenarios ‘One-small’, in which weights are expected to influence the estimation strongly are shown in Figure 5 for RPB. It should be noted that the scenario with a 20% missing probability was excluded from the figure in the CC analysis because it occurred when the parameters could not be estimated. With a 5% missing probability, the bias was almost zero in most conditions, since it is only expected to be missing in only one out of 20 studies per covariate, but a small bias was observed in the estimation of slopes in MI and ExW. The bias was found to increase for MI and ExW when the missing probabilities were 10 and 20%, while the increase in bias was suppressed for wMI,

which adopted weighted regression in its imputation model. The same experiment was conducted for the coverage, and it was confirmed that wMI is the closest to the result of Full (Figure not shown).

Figure 2: The Relative parameter bias (RPB) for the intercept and the slope estimates with the meta-regression model by method handling missing data, missing mechanisms, and the scenarios (5 – 7). The x-axis refers to the method used for handling the missing data.

4. Discussions

In our research, we extend the work of Lee and Beretvas (2023) with respect to the MI algorithm and the missing mechanism for covariates missingness in meta-regression. Our simulation results indicates that if variables are expected to be normally distributed, a parametric method should be used proactively instead of PMM, specifically when the number of units is small, such as in meta-regression. In meta-regression, units correspond to studies, so the number of units tends to be small when considering complementation, even if large studies with a large number of subjects are included. Since the default for R package mice is PMM, it is recommended that the method is changed when the normal distribution assumption is not seriously in doubt. PMM is a robust method even when the data are not normally distributed, but previous studies evaluating the performance of PMM assumed relatively large sample size (e.g. $n = 1000$) (Marshall, Altman, & Holder, 2010) or it was suggested that bias occurs when sample sizes are 50 or 100 (Kleinke, 2017). In the case of meta-analysis, the number of units is often not expected to be sufficiently large (Figure 1).

Among the MIs without predictive mean matching, the weighted regression model (wMI) tended to be closer to the results of positive control (Full) than models without weights (MI). Although clear differences were observed only in special scenarios, i.e., meta-analyses with only one primary study with a small number of subjects (Figure 2), we found no cases that indicate wMI performs worse than CC or unweighted MI (Figure not shown), and the use of weighted regression in the imputation model can be recommended. Although the results of the model that considered weights by adding them to the explanatory variables (ExW) did not seem to differ from the model without weights, further study might be needed, such as adding an interaction term between weights and covariates (Quartagno et al., 2019).

There is more work to be represented but not shown in this paper, specifically simulation results evaluated by coverage. Another limitation of our study is that it does not take into account methods to introduce random-effects into the imputation model since there is no existing software package of MI that can simultaneously apply weights and random-effects to data in the format of meta-analysis, to the best of the authors' knowledge. Particularly in cases where considerable heterogeneity remains even with using covariates as in Figure 1 last scenario, it may not be sufficient only to consider weights in the imputation model.

Overall, our simulation study shows that using the PMM algorithm is not robust when the unit size is small, as in meta-analysis. It should be noted that even for the conditions characterized as 'Large' in Table 1, the number of studies is relatively large in the context of a meta-analysis, but the size of the units is smaller than when assuming the use of individual data.

Our recommendation on whether weighted regression should always be used in a imputation model in the context of meta-regression are at this point as follows. When using multiple imputation methods, weighted regression should be used as long as resources are available, as we have not found any cases where wMI performed worse than MI, and wMI is especially recommended in the case that there are a few studies with considerably smaller weights than the other studies. However, as pointed out in previous studies (White and Carlin, 2010), it was also confirmed that MI or wMI is not always better than CC analysis, specifically in MCAR cases. The missing mechanism needs to be examined in detail according to the characteristics of each individual study.

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